

A Note on a Comparative Study of the Preparation of Anthraquinone.

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Attempts have been made by the authors to make a comparative study of the various methods described in literature for the oxidation of anthracene to anthraquinone. So far Fischer's chromic acid method has been found to be the best in giving the maximum yield but the process involves the use of materials which are comparatively costly. A cheaper and fairly satisfactory method of oxidising anthracene has been devised by using oxides of nitrogen. The yield of anthraquinone obtained by different methods is summarised below :

Reagents.	Yield, of sublimed anthraquinone from 5 g. of pure anthracene.
1. Chromium trioxide and glacial acetic acid (Graebe and Liebermann's method) ...	3.6 g.
2. Chromium trioxide and glacial acetic acid (as modified by Fischer)	4.3 ..
3. Sodium dichromate and sulphuric acid ...	3.0 ..
4. Sodium nitrate and magnesium chloride ...	2.8 ..
5. Nitric acid and glacial acetic acid ...	3.0 ..
6. Dilute nitric acid	2.3 ..
7. Sodium nitrate and sulphuric acid ...	3.2 ..
8. Sodium nitrate and acetic acid	2.4 ..
9. Oxides of nitrogen in presence of water or rectified spirit	3.0 ..
10. Oxides of nitrogen in presence of sulphuric acid, dilute or strong	2.5 ..
11. Oxides of nitrogen in presence of acetic acid or chloroform or carbon tetrachloride or benzene or nitrobenzene	1.5 to 2.5 g.

In the case of the oxides of nitrogen the procedure adopted has been as follows:—

The oxides of nitrogen obtained by warming arsenious oxide and strong nitric acid are passed in anthracene (5 g.) suspended in water (25 c.c.) or rectified spirit (25 c.c.) or other solvents mentioned above. There is no apparent change for the first few minutes. The temperature then begins to rise gradually and remains stationary between 60° and 70° for some time. Meanwhile the substance turns yellowish. The absorption of the gas is not so rapid in the case of water as some of it escapes unabsorbed but it is comparatively rapid in the case of rectified spirit and other solvents. The mixture is shaken from time to time. When no more gases are seen to be absorbed, the reacting mixture is removed and warmed on water-bath for about an hour. Considerable evolution of the oxides of nitrogen takes place during this time. The solid residue left is separated, pressed between filter papers, dried and sublimed.

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